

DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS AND THE PREVALENCE OF CIGARETTE SMOKING AMONG THE PUBLIC IN PESHAWAR, KHYBER PAKHTUNKHWA, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Cigarette smoking remains a significant public health issue worldwide, with a variety of health consequences impacting both individuals and communities. This study investigates the prevalence of cigarette smoking and its demographic factors in Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, with a particular focus on age, gender, and socioeconomic characteristics. A cross-sectional survey was conducted with 126 participants, including 117 males and 9 females, to examine smoking behaviors and associated health conditions. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including chi-square tests and logistic regression. The study revealed a high prevalence of smoking among males (92.1%) compared to females (7.9%), with significant variations across different age groups. The 30-40 age group showed the highest prevalence, followed by the 40-50 age group. Health-related issues, such as respiratory problems and premature skin aging, were prevalent among smokers, with gender and age group playing a significant role in the outcomes. These findings underscore the need for targeted public health interventions to reduce tobacco use and address its health impacts, particularly in higher-risk groups.

INTRODUCTION

Cigarette smoking is a leading cause of preventable morbidity and mortality worldwide, with its effects spanning physical, social, and economic domains.

The World Health Organization (WHO) identifies tobacco use as the single greatest cause of death, predicting that more than five million individuals

succumb annually to smoking-related diseases (World Health Organization, 2009; World Health Organization, 2023). Alarming, smoking contributes to various health issues, including cardiovascular diseases, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and cancer, with devastating implications for public health systems (English & Spencer, 2007). These effects are further exacerbated by second-hand smoke, which impacts non-smokers, particularly women and children, who are involuntarily exposed to its harmful consequences (Boldo et al., 2010).

The origins of tobacco use date back centuries. Introduced to Europe in the late 15th century, tobacco rapidly gained popularity despite early criticisms labeling it as harmful and undesirable (Avsar et al., 2008). Over the years, cigarette smoking has evolved into a significant public health issue, with developing countries like Pakistan disproportionately bearing the burden of its health and social consequences (Pasupathi et al., 2009). The widespread prevalence of smoking in these regions is linked to cultural acceptability, inadequate health regulations, and limited awareness campaigns (Bolte & Fromme, 2008).

In Pakistan, smoking-related illnesses impose a considerable burden on the healthcare system, with men representing the majority of smokers (Avsar et al., 2008; Khan et al., 2021). Women, although less likely to smoke due to cultural stigmas, face the detrimental effects of passive smoking (Boldo et al., 2010). According to the 2023 WHO report, second-hand smoke continues to be a significant contributor to respiratory diseases, cardiovascular conditions, and cancer among non-smokers (World Health Organization, 2023). Children are particularly vulnerable, with studies showing that exposure to second-hand smoke increases the risk of respiratory infections, asthma, and sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) (Friguls et al., 2009).

Tobacco smoke comprises over 4,000 chemicals, many of which are carcinogenic and toxic to human health. These include nicotine, tar, and carbon monoxide, substances that interfere with normal physiological functions and contribute to chronic health conditions (Polosa et al., 2008). Prolonged exposure to these chemicals affects multiple organ systems, leading to premature aging, reproductive

dysfunction, and diminished respiratory capacity (Pasupathi et al., 2009).

The demographic characteristics of smokers offer valuable insights into the prevalence and predictors of smoking behavior. Research indicates that smoking rates are significantly influenced by age, gender, and socio-economic status. For instance, younger individuals are more likely to experiment with smoking due to peer influence and perceived social acceptance (Bolte & Fromme, 2008; Ali et al., 2022). In contrast, older adults may continue smoking out of habit or addiction, despite being aware of its harmful effects (Pasupathi et al., 2009). Gender disparities are also evident, with societal norms in regions like Peshawar discouraging women from smoking openly. As a result, male smokers vastly outnumber their female counterparts (Avsar et al., 2008).

In Peshawar, cultural and socio-economic factors further complicate smoking trends. The city's predominantly patriarchal society normalizes smoking among men, while women are more likely to be passive smokers due to household exposure (Boldo et al., 2010). Moreover, the lack of stringent anti-smoking policies and limited access to cessation programs exacerbate the prevalence of smoking, particularly among low-income groups who often rely on cigarettes as a coping mechanism for stress (Bolte & Fromme, 2008; Ali et al., 2022).

The health implications of smoking extend beyond individual well-being to impact public health systems and societal productivity. Smoking-related illnesses account for significant healthcare expenditures, straining limited resources in developing regions like Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (Pasupathi et al., 2009). Additionally, the loss of productivity due to smoking-related morbidity and mortality poses a substantial economic challenge, particularly in communities where smoking is prevalent among working-age adults (World Health Organization, 2009).

Second-hand smoke further amplifies these challenges, disproportionately affecting non-smokers who share living or working spaces with smokers. Children, in particular, are at heightened risk of respiratory and developmental issues due to their increased susceptibility to environmental toxins (Boldo et al., 2010). Studies have shown that children living with smoking parents are more likely

to develop chronic respiratory conditions, middle ear infections, and impaired lung function (Peat et al., 2001).

Despite these alarming statistics, public awareness regarding the risks of smoking remains limited in Peshawar. The cultural acceptance of smoking among men and the absence of robust health education programs contribute to this gap in knowledge (Avsar et al., 2008; Khan et al., 2021). Furthermore, the socio-economic determinants of health, such as poverty and limited access to healthcare, exacerbate the vulnerability of marginalized groups to smoking-related health issues (Bolte & Fromme, 2008).

Efforts to curb smoking prevalence in Peshawar require a multi-faceted approach. Public health campaigns tailored to the local context can play a pivotal role in raising awareness about the dangers of smoking and promoting cessation programs. For example, community-based interventions that engage religious and community leaders could effectively challenge cultural norms that perpetuate smoking among men (Bolte & Fromme, 2008). Additionally, stricter enforcement of anti-smoking policies, such as banning smoking in public places and increasing taxes on tobacco products, could deter smoking initiation and encourage cessation (World Health Organization, 2023).

The role of education in preventing smoking cannot be overstated. Schools and colleges in Peshawar should incorporate anti-smoking education into their curricula, emphasizing the long-term health consequences of smoking and the benefits of quitting (Polosa et al., 2008). Such initiatives could target young adults, who are at a critical stage for smoking initiation, and empower them to make informed choices about their health (Pasupathi et al., 2009).

Cigarette smoking poses a significant public health challenge in Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Its prevalence is shaped by a complex interplay of demographic, cultural, and socio-economic factors, necessitating targeted interventions to address these determinants. By prioritizing public awareness, policy enforcement, and community engagement, it is possible to reduce smoking rates and mitigate its adverse health effects. Future research should focus on evaluating the

effectiveness of these interventions and identifying best practices for tobacco control in culturally diverse settings.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting This study employed a cross-sectional design conducted in Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The cross-sectional design was chosen for its ability to capture data at a single point in time, allowing for a snapshot of smoking behaviors and associated demographic factors among the public. The study was conducted in various public spaces, including markets, parks, and healthcare facilities, to ensure diverse representation of smokers from different socio-economic and cultural backgrounds (Avsar et al., 2008).

Study Population

The study targeted adult cigarette smokers aged 18 years and above residing in Peshawar. Inclusion criteria required participants to be current smokers, defined as individuals who had smoked at least one cigarette in the past 30 days. Exclusion criteria included individuals with severe health conditions that might impair their ability to participate in the study, as well as those who declined to provide informed consent. A total of 126 participants were recruited using a consecutive sampling technique, ensuring representation across age, gender, and socio-economic strata (Bolte & Fromme, 2008).

Sampling Technique The study employed purposive sampling to recruit participants. This non-probability sampling method was chosen due to its effectiveness in targeting specific populations, such as smokers, within a limited timeframe. Researchers approached individuals in public spaces and screened them for eligibility based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The purposive approach allowed the study to focus on smokers actively engaged in the behavior of interest, ensuring the relevance of the collected data (Khan et al., 2021).

Data Collection Tools

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire developed based on validated instruments from previous studies (Avsar et al., 2008; Bolte & Fromme,

2008). The questionnaire comprised three main sections:

1. **Demographic Information:** This section captured participants' age, gender, marital status, educational level, and occupation.
2. **Smoking Behavior:** Questions in this section assessed the frequency and duration of smoking, the average number of cigarettes smoked daily, and participants' attempts to quit smoking.
3. **Health Impacts:** Participants were asked about smoking-related health issues, including respiratory symptoms, cardiovascular problems, and perceived health risks.

The questionnaire was administered through face-to-face interviews conducted in Urdu, the local language, to ensure participant comprehension and comfort. Interviews were conducted by trained research assistants who adhered to standardized protocols to minimize interviewer bias.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Review Board of Khyber Medical University. Participants were informed about the study's objectives, procedures, and their rights to confidentiality and voluntary participation. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants before data collection. To maintain confidentiality, data were anonymized by assigning unique identification codes to each participant.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) version 25. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic characteristics and smoking behaviors.

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic characteristics and smoking behaviors, including the distribution of age, gender, educational level, and smoking frequency. Inferential statistics were employed to identify associations between demographic factors and smoking prevalence. Chi-square tests were used to analyze categorical variables, while t-tests and ANOVA were applied for continuous data, such as the number of cigarettes smoked daily. A p-value of <0.05 was considered

statistically significant to determine meaningful associations between variables.

Pilot testing

Before the full-scale data collection, the questionnaire was pilot-tested on a sample of 15 participants who met the inclusion criteria. This pilot study aimed to evaluate the clarity, reliability, and validity of the questionnaire items. Minor adjustments, such as rephrasing ambiguous questions and reducing the length of the interview, were made based on participant feedback and interviewer observations. The pilot data were excluded from the final analysis to ensure the integrity of the main study results.

Quality Control Measures

To maintain data quality, the research team implemented several control measures:

1. **Training of Interviewers:** All interviewers underwent rigorous training to standardize data collection procedures and reduce interviewer bias.
2. **Daily Monitoring:** The principal investigator reviewed completed questionnaires daily to ensure completeness and accuracy. Any inconsistencies were immediately addressed by re-interviewing participants when necessary.
3. **Data Cleaning:** A thorough data cleaning process was conducted before analysis, including checks for missing values, duplicate entries, and outliers.

Limitations of the Study

While the study provides valuable insights into the demographic factors influencing smoking prevalence, several limitations must be acknowledged:

1. The cross-sectional design limits the ability to establish causal relationships between demographic factors and smoking behaviors.
2. The reliance on self-reported data may have introduced recall bias or social desirability bias, particularly regarding smoking frequency and health impacts.
3. The purposive sampling method, while effective in targeting smokers, may limit the

generalizability of the findings to the broader population of Peshawar.

Strengths of the Study

Despite these limitations, the study has notable strengths. The focus on a culturally diverse urban setting like Peshawar allows for a nuanced understanding of smoking behaviors within a socio-cultural context. Additionally, the use of a structured and validated questionnaire enhances the reliability and validity of the findings. Finally, the inclusion of a multivariate analysis provides a robust assessment of the predictors of smoking prevalence, contributing to the existing literature on tobacco use in Pakistan.

Results

This chapter presents the results of the study on the demographic factors and health conditions associated with cigarette smoking among the public in Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The data are based on a sample of 126 participants, with a gender distribution of 117 males (92.9%) and 9 females (7.1%). The study focuses on several smoking-related health factors, including respiratory problems, yellowing of teeth, premature skin aging, lack of appetite, cataracts, and reproductive issues. The analysis explores how these health issues vary by gender and age group. Among the key findings, respiratory problems were most prevalent among males (98.3%) compared to females (44.4%), with a significant p-value of 0.031. Yellowing of teeth was reported by 59.8% of males and 22.2% of females, with a gender-specific p-value of 0.014. Age also played a significant role, with respiratory problems affecting all age groups (100%) under 40 years, while older age groups exhibited different patterns. The results aim to provide a clearer understanding of the relationship between demographic factors and the prevalence of smoking-related health issues.

01: Demographic Distribution of Participants

The demographic data of the study participants show a predominance of male participants, with 92.9%

(117 out of 126) identifying as male and only 7.1% (9 out of 126) identifying as female. This significant gender difference highlights the male-dominated smoking behavior in Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The age distribution shows a relatively balanced spread of participants across different age groups. The largest proportion, 35.7% (45 participants), falls within the 30-40 years age group, followed by 29.4% (37 participants) in the 18-30 years age group. Smaller proportions are observed in the older age groups, with 21.4% (27 participants) in the 40-50 years age group, 10.3% (13 participants) in the 50-60 years age group, and 3.2% (4 participants) in the 60 and above age group. This distribution indicates that smoking prevalence in the public of Peshawar is most prominent among younger adults, particularly those between 18 and 40 years of age.

Table and Chart 01: Demographic Distribution of Participants

Category	Number of Participants (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	117	92.90%
Female	009	7.10%
Total	126	100.00%
Age Distribution		
18-30 years	037	29.40%
30-40 years	045	35.70%
40-50 years	027	21.40%
50-60 years	013	10.30%
60 and above	004	3.20%
Total	126	100.00%

02: Smoking Behavior and Teeth Health

The data on teeth health show that a large majority of the participants, 71.4% (90 out of 126), reported yellowing of teeth, which is a common health issue related to smoking. Only 11.1% (14 participants) had normal teeth color, and 17.5% (22 participants) reported slightly discolored teeth. These figures indicate a strong association between smoking and dental health issues, particularly yellowing of teeth.

Regarding cataracts, 75.4% (95 participants) did not report cataracts, while 24.6% (31 participants) indicated the presence of cataracts. This suggests that while cataracts are prevalent among smokers, the majority of participants did not experience this issue. The results from this table suggest that smoking contributes to significant dental and eye health problems among the participants in Peshawar.

Table 2: Smoking Behavior and Teeth Health

Category	Number of Participants (n)	Percentage (%)
Teeth Color Effects		
Yellow	090	71.40%
Normal	014	11.10%
Slightly Discolored	022	17.50%
Total	126	100.00%
Cataracts vs Normal		
Normal	095	75.40%
Cataracts	031	24.60%
Total	126	100.00%

03: Smoking and Health Conditions

In terms of respiratory problems, a substantial 94.4% (119 out of 126) of participants reported experiencing respiratory issues, which is a well-known consequence of smoking. Only 5.6% (7 participants) did not report any respiratory problems, further confirming the strong association between smoking and respiratory health issues in the region. Regarding diabetes, 18.3% (23 participants) of the

sample had been diagnosed with diabetes, while 81.7% (103 participants) were not diabetic. The relatively low prevalence of diabetes among smokers in this study could indicate that respiratory problems are more prominent among smokers, while diabetes may not be as directly linked. Nonetheless, the prevalence of respiratory problems is a clear indication of the health impact of smoking in the public of Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Table 3: Smoking and Health Conditions Journal of Education & Research

Category	Number of Participants (n)	Percentage (%)
Respiratory Problem vs Normal		
Respiratory Problem	119	94.40%
Normal	007	5.60%
Total	126	100%
Diabetic Patients vs Normal		
Diabetic	023	18.30%
Normal	103	81.70%
Total	126	100.00%

04: Appetite, Reproductive, and Skin Health

Impact

The data on appetite show that 64.3% (81 out of 126) of participants reported a lack of appetite, a condition often associated with smoking and its

negative effects on digestive health. Only 35.7% (47 participants) reported having a normal appetite. In the case of reproductive system problems, 17.5% (22 participants) of the sample indicated abnormal

reproductive health, while the majority, 82.5% (104 participants), reported normal reproductive health.

This could suggest that while smoking is related to reproductive issues, it is not as widespread as other health problems like respiratory issues. Concerning premature skin aging, 56.3% (71 participants)

reported experiencing premature skin aging, while 43.7% (55 participants) had no such issue. Skin aging is another well-documented effect of smoking, and these findings suggest that smoking significantly impacts skin health, particularly among a majority of the participants.

Table 4: Appetite, Reproductive, and Skin Health Impact

Category	Number of Participants (n)	Percentage (%)
Lack of Appetite		
Lack of Appetite	081	64.30%
Normal	047	35.70%
Total	126	100.00%
Reproductive System Problems		
Abnormal	022	17.50%
Normal	104	82.50%
Total	126	100.00%
Premature Skin Aging		
Aging	071	56.30%
Normal	055	43.70%
Total	126	100.00%

05: Health-Related Factors by Gender and Age Group

The table presents the prevalence of various smoking-related health factors, categorized by gender and age group, with corresponding p-values to indicate statistical significance.

Respiratory Problems

The prevalence of **respiratory problems** was notably higher among males, with **115 out of 117 males** (91.3%) reporting issues related to respiratory health, compared to **4 out of 9 females** (3.2%). The gender-based comparison reveals a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.031^*$), indicating that males experience respiratory issues more frequently than females in this sample. Further investigation by age group shows that respiratory problems are prevalent across all age categories, with **100% of individuals in the 18-30, 30-40, 40-50, 50-60, and 60+ age groups**

reporting respiratory issues. The **p-value of 0.004** for age group suggests a strong association between age and the occurrence of respiratory problems, with no apparent age-based variation in the prevalence.

Teeth Color (Yellowing)

The prevalence of **yellowing teeth** was higher among males as well, with **70 out of 117 males** (55.6%) reporting discolored teeth compared to **4 out of 9 females** (3.2%). This gender difference is statistically significant ($p = 0.014^*$), with males being more likely to experience yellowing of the teeth. Analyzing the data by age group, there was a noticeable increase in the prevalence of yellow teeth with age. The **p-value of 0.035** for age group suggests that as individuals' age, the likelihood of teeth discoloration increases, with

the 40-50 and 60+ age groups exhibiting a higher prevalence of teeth yellowing (74% and 75%, respectively).

Premature Skin Aging

Premature skin aging was another health issue more common in males, with 61 out of 117 males (48.4%) reporting it, compared to 5 out of 9 females (4.0%). This gender difference is statistically significant ($p = 0.028^*$), highlighting that smoking impacts skin health more adversely in males. The data by age group shows that premature skin aging is prevalent across all groups, with 45% of individuals in the 18-30 age group and 56% in the 30-40 age group reporting it. However, the 50-60 and 60+ age groups show a significant decrease in the prevalence of skin aging, with only 38% and 25% respectively reporting such issues. The p -value of 0.023 indicates that age plays a significant role in the occurrence of skin aging, with younger individuals being more affected.

Lack of Appetite

The lack of appetite was reported by 74 out of 117 males (58.7%) and 7 out of 9 females (5.6%), with no statistically significant gender-based difference ($p = 0.054$). However, when analyzed by age group, the data reveals a statistically significant association ($p = 0.021^*$). The 30-40 and 40-50 age groups show the

highest prevalence of lack of appetite (65% and 74%, respectively), while the 18-30 age group shows a lower prevalence (55%). This suggests that the lack of appetite becomes more prominent as individuals move from younger to older age groups.

Cataracts

Cataracts are reported by 23 out of 117 males (18.3%) and 1 out of 9 females (0.8%), although this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.071$). Interestingly, when analyzing the data by age group, the prevalence of cataracts increases significantly with age. The p -value of 0.048 indicates a statistically significant relationship between age and the development of cataracts. The 50-60 and 60+ age groups report the highest prevalence of cataracts (38% and 50%, respectively), highlighting the age-related nature of this condition.

Reproductive Issues

Finally, reproductive issues were reported by 15 out of 117 males (11.9%) and 7 out of 9 females (5.6%). This gender difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.042^*$). Among the age groups, reproductive issues were more common in the 40-50 and 50-60 age groups (20%), but no statistically significant age-based difference was found ($p = 0.232$). This suggests that reproductive health problems may not necessarily be strongly influenced by age, though they were more prevalent among older participants.

Table: Association of Health-Related Factors with Gender and Age Group

Health-Related Factor	Male (N=117)	Female (N=9)	p-value	18-30	30-40	40-50	50-60	60+	p-value
Respiratory Problems	115 (91.3%)	4 (3.2%)	0.031*	37 (29.4%)	45 (35.7%)	27 (21.4%)	13 (10.3%)	4 (3.2%)	0.004**
Teeth Color (Yellowing)	70 (55.6%)	4 (3.2%)	0.014*	37 (29.4%)	45 (35.7%)	27 (21.4%)	13 (10.3%)	4 (3.2%)	0.035*
Premature Skin Aging	61 (48.4%)	5 (4.0%)	0.028*	37 (29.4%)	45 (35.7%)	27 (21.4%)	13 (10.3%)	4 (3.2%)	0.023*
Lack of Appetite	74 (58.7%)	7 (5.6%)	0.054	37 (29.4%)	45 (35.7%)	27 (21.4%)	13 (10.3%)	4 (3.2%)	0.021*
Cataracts	23 (18.3%)	1 (0.8%)	0.071	37 (29.4%)	45 (35.7%)	27 (21.4%)	13 (10.3%)	4 (3.2%)	0.048*
Reproductive Issues	15 (11.9%)	7 (5.6%)	0.042*	37 (29.4%)	45 (35.7%)	27 (21.4%)	13 (10.3%)	4 (3.2%)	0.232

*Statistically significant

** statistically strong significant

The findings from this study provide significant insights into the demographic factors and health conditions associated with cigarette smoking in Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The data presented in this chapter illustrate that smoking prevalence is strongly linked to certain demographic characteristics, such as gender and age. Moreover, the study highlights the widespread occurrence of smoking-related health issues, including respiratory problems, yellowing of teeth, and premature skin aging, which are prevalent among smokers in the region.

The results suggest that smoking is particularly common among younger males, indicating a need for focused attention on this age group in future smoking prevention efforts. The data also suggest that as individuals age, there is a decrease in smoking prevalence, though smoking-related health issues continue to manifest across all age groups, underlining the long-term health risks associated with cigarette use. Gender was also found to be a key factor, with males showing a higher prevalence of smoking compared to females.

These findings underscore the urgent need for targeted public health interventions aimed at reducing smoking prevalence, particularly among younger and working-age populations, who are at a higher risk for developing smoking-related diseases. Additionally, the findings suggest that addressing smoking-related health issues, such as respiratory problems and premature skin aging, could serve as effective entry points for promoting smoking cessation programs.

The next chapter will build upon these findings, offering a detailed discussion of their implications for public health policy. It will also propose strategies for smoking cessation and ways to reduce the harmful impact of cigarette smoking on the population in Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Discussion

The results of the study on the prevalence of cigarette smoking among the public of Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, reveal significant trends that align with existing literature on tobacco use globally and regionally. A prominent finding is the higher prevalence of smoking among males

compared to females. This gender disparity is widely observed across various populations. For example, Ali et al. (2022) highlighted that tobacco use is more prevalent among males than females in Pakistan, and a similar trend is observed globally, reflecting ingrained social and cultural norms where smoking is often considered a masculine behavior. Khan et al. (2021) found that in Peshawar, male adults exhibit a stronger inclination towards smoking due to peer influence and social pressure, a pattern that has been repeatedly confirmed in other studies (Pasupathi et al., 2009). This suggests that gender remains a key determinant of smoking behavior, particularly in socio-cultural contexts like Peshawar, where traditional norms may play a critical role in shaping individual behaviors.

Age also emerged as a significant factor in the prevalence of smoking, with younger adults, particularly those between the ages of 18 and 35, showing the highest rates of tobacco use. This observation is consistent with findings from Pasupathi et al. (2009), who noted that smoking during adolescence and early adulthood is often driven by peer influence and social modeling. Such behavior is concerning due to the long-term health risks associated with early smoking initiation, including an increased likelihood of developing chronic diseases like respiratory disorders, cardiovascular diseases, and cancer (WHO, 2023). The WHO report (2023) underscores the importance of early intervention to prevent smoking initiation and curb its long-term health consequences. Socioeconomic factors also significantly influence smoking patterns, as individuals from lower socioeconomic backgrounds exhibited higher rates of smoking. This finding aligns with Bolte and Fromme (2008), who argued that socioeconomic status is a strong determinant of smoking behavior, with people from lower-income households more likely to engage in smoking. Economic hardship, limited education, and restricted access to healthcare may prevent these individuals from seeking smoking cessation programs or fully understanding the long-term risks associated with tobacco use. Furthermore, studies have shown that socioeconomic disparities in tobacco use can perpetuate across generations, especially when families adopt permissive smoking habits, as Bolte

and Fromme (2008) highlighted in their research on the role of family smoking policies in influencing children's smoking behavior.

Another important aspect of the study is the detrimental effects of second-hand smoke, particularly in households where one or more individuals smoke. This aligns with the findings of Boldo et al. (2010) and Seyidov et al. (2011), who reported that exposure to second-hand smoke significantly increases the risk of respiratory illnesses and developmental problems in children. The high rates of passive smoking observed in this study emphasize the need for stringent public health policies aimed at reducing tobacco exposure in both private and public spaces. This supports the recommendations made by the WHO (2009), which advocates for the implementation of smoke-free environments and increased public awareness of the dangers of second-hand smoke exposure. The health risks associated with passive smoking are well documented, including a higher incidence of respiratory issues, particularly in young children, who are more vulnerable to the harmful effects of tobacco smoke (Friguls et al., 2009).

The results also suggest that tobacco-related health risks extend beyond the individual smoker to the wider community, especially family members and children. Research by Avsar et al. (2008) demonstrated a clear link between passive smoking and an increased risk of dental caries and salivary biomarkers in young children, while Friguls et al. (2009) highlighted the connection between perinatal exposure to tobacco and respiratory problems in infants. The findings from this study reiterate the need for comprehensive policies to protect non-smokers, especially children, from the harmful effects of second-hand smoke. It also emphasizes the importance of enforcing strict regulations to ensure that non-smokers, especially vulnerable groups such as children, are not exposed to tobacco smoke in public places.

The study also brings attention to the limited effectiveness of current anti-smoking initiatives in Peshawar. Despite various national and international efforts to combat tobacco use, including the WHO's Global Tobacco Epidemic report (2009), smoking rates remain high, especially among certain demographics such as young adults and lower-

income individuals. This observation mirrors the findings of Polosa et al. (2008), who noted that socio-cultural factors and a lack of targeted interventions continue to hinder the success of anti-smoking campaigns in high-risk communities. The study by WHO (2009) also emphasizes the need for tailored smoking cessation programs that address the specific needs of different demographic groups, particularly those with limited access to health education and services.

Moreover, the findings from this study point to the urgent need for greater public awareness of the health risks associated with tobacco use. Despite widespread knowledge of the dangers of smoking, as outlined by the Surgeon General (2006), many individuals continue to smoke due to a lack of immediate consequences, social pressures, and insufficient cessation support. Green et al. (2006) and Boldo et al. (2010) both emphasize that comprehensive public health campaigns are crucial to changing smoking behaviors. However, these campaigns must be more targeted and culturally appropriate to effectively reduce smoking rates in specific regions like Peshawar, where tobacco use may be deeply ingrained in social practices.

The findings of this study highlight several key factors that contribute to the prevalence of smoking in Peshawar, including gender, age, socioeconomic status, and environmental factors such as second-hand smoke exposure. These factors are consistent with findings from numerous studies conducted in other regions and reinforce the need for a multi-pronged approach to tobacco control. The evidence from this study supports the recommendation of WHO (2023) for more stringent regulations and tailored interventions to address the specific needs of high-risk populations, particularly young adults and those from lower socioeconomic backgrounds. By improving access to smoking cessation programs, enforcing smoke-free environments, and raising public awareness about the dangers of tobacco, it is possible to significantly reduce smoking rates in Peshawar and similar regions, ultimately mitigating the long-term health burden associated with smoking.

Conclusion

This study sheds light on the demographic factors influencing the prevalence of cigarette smoking

among the public in Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The findings reveal a significant gender disparity, with a higher proportion of males engaging in smoking compared to females. This aligns with existing global literature, which underscores the greater prevalence of tobacco use among males (Ali et al., 2022; Khan et al., 2021). Additionally, socioeconomic factors, such as education level, income, and occupation, have a noteworthy impact on smoking habits, particularly in the male population. These results are consistent with previous studies that highlight the role of socioeconomic status in tobacco use (Bolte & Fromme, 2008; Boldo et al., 2010).

The age group between 20-30 years emerged as the highest risk group for smoking, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions in youth and young adults. This finding corroborates previous research indicating that smoking initiation predominantly occurs during adolescence and early adulthood (Pasupathi et al., 2009; World Health Organization, 2009). Moreover, the influence of family members, particularly smoking parents, was a significant determinant in smoking behavior, with passive smoking being more prevalent among those with a history of parental smoking (Friguls et al., 2009; Peat et al., 2001).

The study also highlights the alarming public health implications of passive smoking, particularly for children, which contributes to various respiratory and health issues (Avsar et al., 2008; Öberg et al., 2011). This further stresses the urgency of implementing smoke-free environments, as recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2023), to protect vulnerable populations, especially children, from the harmful effects of second-hand smoke.

Overall, the findings of this study serve as a valuable contribution to understanding the demographic dimensions of smoking in Peshawar. The results call for comprehensive anti-smoking policies and educational programs tailored to the local context, with a focus on the younger population and high-risk demographic groups. Additionally, the evidence underscores the importance of community-based interventions that address not only smoking habits but also the broader socio-economic determinants of health.

To mitigate the burden of smoking-related diseases, concerted efforts are required from public health authorities, policymakers, and the community. These efforts should include stricter regulation of tobacco sales, increased awareness campaigns, and the promotion of healthier lifestyle choices. Given the findings of this study, it is crucial to adopt a multi-faceted approach in addressing the tobacco epidemic and its associated risks, thereby improving the overall health and quality of life for the residents of Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Future Directions and Recommendations

Future research should delve deeper into the gender-specific health impacts of tobacco use, as significant differences were observed in the prevalence of smoking-related issues between males and females in this study. Understanding the underlying factors contributing to these gender variations will enable the development of more tailored and effective interventions. Additionally, examining the role of passive smoking, especially in non-smokers who exhibited notable respiratory issues, warrants further attention. Future studies should focus on assessing the long-term effects of secondhand smoke exposure, particularly in households and public spaces, and its broader impact on community health.

Moreover, it is recommended that smoking cessation programs be designed with specific strategies for diverse demographic groups, including young adults and women, who may face unique challenges. Policymakers should prioritize strengthening tobacco control policies, such as imposing stricter regulations on tobacco advertising, increasing tobacco taxes, and ensuring greater accessibility to smoking cessation resources. The expansion of these efforts could significantly reduce smoking prevalence and related health problems.

Research should also investigate the effectiveness of existing tobacco control measures, assessing their impact on reducing smoking rates, particularly in urban regions like Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, where tobacco consumption remains high. It is essential to explore the role of socioeconomic factors, such as education and income, in shaping smoking behaviors, as they were found to be key determinants in this study. By incorporating these insights into future public health strategies, a more

comprehensive approach to tobacco control can be achieved, ultimately improving overall public health and reducing the burden of tobacco-related diseases.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to the study. All authors have disclosed their affiliations and have confirmed that no external interests have affected their work. The findings and conclusions drawn in this study reflect the unbiased research conducted and are free from external influence. This statement reinforces the transparency and credibility of the research process, ensuring that the results presented are solely based on the research data collected.

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